

Wide Electrochemical Stability Window of Boron-Doped Microcrystalline Diamond Electrode in NaNO₃ Water-in-Salt Electrolytes

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ABSTRACT: Expanding the electrochemical stability window (ESW) of aqueous electrolytes can contribute to the high energy density of electrochemical energy-storage devices and supercapacitors. Here, we demonstrate a unique electrochemical interaction in two- and three-electrode configurations of sodium nitrate (NaNO₃) water-in-salt (WiS) electrolyte in a wide range of concentrations (1–12 m) with an electrode made of boron-doped microcrystalline diamond (B-MCDE, grain size ~1 mm) deposited by a microwave plasma chemical vapor deposition process. Compared to the commercial glassy carbon electrode (C-GCE), the ESW reached ~3 V. In the frequency range of 10 mHz–100 kHz, the B-MCDE also demonstrated better conductive (down to R_{ct} of 50 Ω) and capacitive (up to C_{dl} 3.2 μ F) properties compared to the C-GCE for all WiS electrolyte concentrations, where the appropriate equivalent circuit was identified. The best performance was obtained for the 8 m WiS concentration at neutral pH and room temperature, while the 12 m WiS was unstable, as confirmed by Raman spectroscopy. The expanded ESW and superior performance of B-MCDE are explained by its high-quality material properties and nanostructured surface (almost nanoporous, feature size <100 nm) formed in the WiS electrolyte. The results reveal that with a well-controlled quality, boron-doped diamond electrodes are advantageous for WiS supercapacitors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern energy-storage devices require increased energy density and power.^{1,2} At the same time, it is necessary to ensure high reliability and low cost. Electrical double-layer capacitors, so-called SCs, are important electrochemical energy-storage devices due to their fast charging and discharging capabilities and ultralong lifetime.^{3,4} However, the low energy density remains a significant problem for SCs.^{5,6} One of the simplest yet highly effective approaches to increasing the energy density is using high-voltage organic electrolytes, which are currently used for commercial 2.3–3.0 V SCs.⁷ However, organic electrolytes' main problems are flammability and volatility.⁸ Some pure ionic liquids used as electrolytes at room temperature provide the operating voltage of SCs up to 4.0 V, but they have high viscosity, which seriously degrades the ion transport, leading to slow energy uptake of SCs.³ In particular, organic electrolytes and ionic liquids are quite sensitive to moisture, which requires additional complex manufacturing processes.⁹ Aqueous electrolytes, in general, can be used as an alternative to solve the problems listed above. Aqueous electrolytes are available, cheaper, and environmentally friendly.⁹ However, the electrochemical stability windows (ESWs) of aqueous electrolytes are significantly narrower than those of organic electrolytes due to the low decomposition voltage of pure water of ~1.23 V.^{8,10}

In contrast to low-concentration electrolytes, highly concentrated electrolytes exhibit extraordinary functionality. Water-in-salt (WiS) electrolytes are a new class of superconcentrated systems.^{3,4,6,7,11–16} They exhibit extremely broad ESWs due to the significantly reduced water content and effective confinement of the chemical activity of the water molecules. The first WiS electrolyte was obtained by dissolving LiTFSI in water with a high salt-to-water molar ratio of 1/2.6 (i.e., 21 m (mol kg⁻¹)), which demonstrated a wide ESW of 3.0 V when using stainless steel electrodes.³ In this paper, Guo et al. showed that increasing the salt concentration allows the ESW to be broadened, enabling high-voltage electrodes to obtain significantly higher energy densities. Compared to the LiTFSI electrolyte, NaNO₃ has the advantage of higher conductivity, lower viscosity, and lower commercial price.³ WiS NaNO₃ electrolyte is optimal among those using WiS electrolytes with higher solubility, such as 17 m NaClO₄, 21 m

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Figure 1. Material characteristics of the electrodes: optical photographs of (a) an encapsulated B-MCDE and (b) a C-GCE. SEM morphologies of B-MCDE at different magnifications (c,d) before and (f,g) after electrochemical measurements. (e) Raman spectra (excitation 442 nm) of B-MCDE and C-GCE after electrochemical measurements. SEM surface morphologies of (h) B-MCDE and (i) C-GCE at different magnifications after electrochemical measurements.

LiTFSI, and 27 m KOAc. At the same time, the most commonly used traditional high-concentration aqueous electrolytes, such as 1 m Li_2SO_4 , 8 m K_2CO_3 , and 6 m $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (the same type of nitrate with high solubility), cannot be compared themselves with 12 m NaNO_3 .¹⁷ SCs using highly concentrated $\text{NaNO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ electrolyte showed the highest specific capacitance and excellent rate performance.

However, using highly concentrated electrolytes requires the search for new electrode materials that would sustain a high voltage and improve the efficiency of SCs based on WiS NaNO_3 electrolytes. Another disadvantage of WiS electrolytes is that the extremely high concentration of salts causes low electrical conductivity and, at the same time, very high viscosity.³ All of the above leads to deterioration of the speed characteristics of the SCs. Diamond electrodes are highly attractive for SCs and batteries¹⁸ due to their generally wide ESWs in various media, diverse ways of nanostructuring to increase capacitance¹⁹ and enhance electrode processes,²⁰ high stability at different charge/discharge conditions and in different acidic/alkaline media as well as high thermal conductivity. Boron-doped diamond electrodes became promising electrodes for energy-storage device applications

due to their high electrical conductivity, wide ESW (3–3.5 V in aqueous media and 5–7.5 V in organic media) compared to metal electrodes, electrocatalytic activity, corrosion resistance, controlled surface wettability, and possible enlargement of surface area.^{21,22} However, the effects of nanoscale surface termination, graphite-to-diamond ratio, surface defects, and morphology of diamond nanostructures on their electrochemical properties are still underexplored and a subject of ongoing studies.^{23,24}

This work thus presents a study of the ESW for WiS electrolyte NaNO_3 in a wide concentration range of 1–12 molality in terms of its structural and chemical features of the boron-doped microcrystalline diamond electrode (B-MCDE) surface. For this purpose, cyclic voltammetry and impedance spectroscopy were employed using B-MCDE and commercial glassy carbon electrode (C-GCE) as working electrodes for comparison. The material, physical, and chemical properties were evaluated by Raman spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The pH and conductivity of the WiS electrolytes were also assessed. The obtained large ESW of up to 3 V and the small charge-transfer resistance (down to 50 Ω) are promising for using the NaNO_3 aqueous electrolyte for SCs

and batteries based on B-MCD electrodes, even at low WiS electrolyte concentrations.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. B-Doped Diamond Electrodes. The deposition of B-MCD films was carried out using a microwave plasma chemical vapor deposition (CVD) system (Seki Diamond Systems SDS6K) (Figure S1a). Polished p-type Si (100) wafers cut into $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ pieces were used as substrates. Prior to the diamond growth process, all of the silicon substrates were nucleated using the diamond “seeding” process: the Si substrates were washed with acetone for 10 min and isopropyl alcohol for 10 min in an ultrasonic bath and rinsed with deionized water, and then the surface was nucleated with 5 nm diamond powder in aqueous solution for 40 min in an ultrasonic bath, rinsed again with deionized water, and dried with nitrogen. For the diamond growth, the boron dopant source was trimethyl boron (TMB) mixed in hydrogen [H_2 (99.999%) + 0.2% TMB (2000 ppm)]. The details of diamond growth process parameters are as follows: Power – 3 kW, pressure – 60 Torr, CH_4 – 10 standard cubic centimeters per minute (sccm), H_2 – 440 sccm, TMB – 50 sccm, B/C = 10,000 ppm (B doping $> 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), and growth time – 10 h. As a growth reference, nominally undoped (intrinsic) microcrystalline diamond films were also grown under similar conditions, except for the TMB addition. Samples of B-MCD grown with different TMBs were performed in order to select the most suitable one for electrochemical testing with the best conductivity (Figure S1b, photo of prepared B-MCD on Si substrate insert in the upper left corner; Figure S1c, comparison of Raman spectra for intrinsic diamond and B-MCD). Resulting conductivity of the boron-doped diamond electrode was evaluated by a four-point (Van der Pauw) method. The obtained sheet resistance of the B-MCD sample, which was used for electrochemical testing, was $5.2 \Omega/\text{sq}$ and resistivity $0.0031 \Omega \text{ cm}$.

The B-MCD samples were then cut into a size of $5 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$. A printed circuit board (Copper film on Cuprexit) was used as an electrode holder, from which $5 \times 40 \text{ mm}^2$ was cut out. The conductive bonding of the substrate on the holder was made using a silver (Ag) conductive paste (Dotite Silver Paint D-550). After applying the silver conductive paste, the electrode was heated at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min. A polymer protective coating (ESL 240-SB, polymer protective coating) was then applied to fix and insulate the holder and B-MCD electrode except for the open, active part of the electrode (2.27 mm^2), and the electrode was heated at $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h. A general view of the B MCD electrode made by us is shown in Figure 1a.

A C-GCE in the PEEK rod (Windsor Scientific, LTD) was used for comparison.

2.2. Characterizations. Surface morphologies of the B-MCD samples were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, MAIA3, and Tescan). All SEM images of B-MCD film/electrodes were acquired at 10 kV under 90° (top-view) and 0° (cross-section) in the regime of secondary electrons. Raman spectra of the B-MCD samples were recorded using a high-resolution Raman spectrometer (Renishaw In Via Reflex Raman) with a 532 nm laser at 2 mW, a microscope objective with $100\times$ magnification, and a grating 600 gr/mm. Raman spectra for comparison of B-MCD and C-GCEs after electrochemical testing were recorded using a Raman spectrometer (Renishaw In Via Reflex Raman) with

442 nm laser, power laser 10%, acquisition 100 s, 4 accumulations, at 2 mW, microscope objective with $100\times/0.9$ magnification, and grating 600 gr/mm. The molecular structure of NaNO_3 electrolytes with different concentrations was analyzed by a high-resolution Raman spectrometer (WITec Alpha 300 RAS) using a 532 nm laser at 1.5 mW, microscope objective with $20\times$ magnification, and grating 600 gr/mm and integration time 60 s. Deconvolution was applied to each Raman spectrum with three Gaussian - Lorentzian functions in the program Origin.

The pH and conductivity of all NaNO_3 electrolytes were measured using a pH meter (HANNA Laboratory EDGE pH) and a conductometer (Cond 3310 SET 1).

2.3. Electrochemical Measurements. Different concentrations of aqueous electrolytes NaNO_3 were prepared for electrochemical analyses at 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 mol/kg of solution. Three-electrode cell configurations were used for ESW measurements: working electrodes (B-MCDE and C-GCE), counterelectrode (Pt), and reference electrode (no-leak Ag/AgCl). Anodic oxidation was performed by applying a high potential of +3.0 V for 3 min in 2.0 M HNO_3 before each measurement. ESW measurements were made using a potentiostat (EMStat Blue controlled by the PSTrace, 5.9 interface) with the following parameters: potential range of ± 3 V; potential step: 10 mV; scan rate: 5.0 mV/s. Before recording the data, each cyclic voltammetry (CV) test was initially cycled three times to ensure a steady state of the system.

The ESW was evaluated from the CV curves, considering an onset at a current density of $+0.1 \text{ mA}/\text{cm}^2$ on the positive potential side and $-0.1 \text{ mA}/\text{cm}^2$ on the negative potential side. Since the electrodes had different areas, $A_{\text{B-MCDE}} = 0.023 \text{ cm}^2$ and $A_{\text{C-BDDE}} = 0.071 \text{ cm}^2$, the onset current values were taken at $+2.3 \mu\text{A}$ i $-2.3 \mu\text{A}$ for B-MCDE and $+7.1 \mu\text{A}$ i $-7.1 \mu\text{A}$ for C-GCE.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) tests were performed using a potentiostat/galvanostat AUTOLAB Metrohm 302N controlled by a Nova 2.1.6 interface. EIS was recorded in the frequency range from 10 mHz to 100 kHz in the two-electrode configuration with a potential amplitude of 10 mV. EIS measurements of all aqueous electrolytes NaNO_3 with IDE (Au and Pt) sensors were made by using an IM 3536 LCR meter and application software (Hioki) in the frequency range up to 100 kHz. All measurements were done at room temperature ($t = 23 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Electrode Characterization. Figure S1a,b shows the photographs of the CVD system chamber, a general view of the grown B-MCD film on a Si substrate (photo of the sample in the upper left corner of Figure S1b), and an AFM image of its surface (Figure S1b). Figure S1d–f shows the SEM morphologies from the top and at the cross-section of the B-MCD electrode. The SEM morphologies show the general microcrystalline nature of the sample with high roughness and well-defined faceted crystallites. The nonuniform secondary electron emission contrast on various grain facets indicates differences in electronic properties at the nanoscale level within the microcrystals. The SEM cross-sectional image also illustrates the microcrystalline character of the film. The thickness of the B-MCD electrode was estimated to be $5.4 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ from the SEM cross sections.

Figure 2. Comparison of electrochemical and chemical parameters for NaNO₃ aqueous electrolytes in the concentration range of 1–12 mol/kg: CV on (a) B-MCDE and (b) C-GCE; (c) pH and (d) conductivity of the NaNO₃ aqueous electrolyte.

Raman spectra of the intrinsic and boron-doped diamond sample show a sharp diamond peak (sp^3) at $\sim 1333\text{ cm}^{-1}$, with the D-band at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Other bands are related to trans-polyacetylene on grain boundaries and graphitic carbon (G-band) at $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Figure S1c). The applied deposition parameters and TMB doping affected the amount of produced amorphous sp^2 graphite (G-band at $\sim 1560\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and disordered graphite (D-band at 1350 cm^{-1}).^{25,26} From the Raman spectra of the intrinsic microcrystalline diamond, it appears that the intrinsic diamond shows optimum diamond quality, which is consistent with the literature, confirming suitable chamber pressure to promote complete activation of the species as well as their collision/rearrangement to form good quality diamond thin films.¹⁰ In doped films, TMB plays an important role in the doped diamond intensity peak as in the chamber leads to higher production of sp^2 species with a consequent decrease of the diamond quality. The free carrier concentration is directly related to the nominal doping level due to microscopic structure, defects, and material composition effects. The resulting resistivity of the B-MCD electrode was $5.2\ \Omega/\text{sq}$. The low resistivity is in the range typical for electrochemical diamond electrodes, confirming the suitability of the B-MCD electrodes for NaNO₃ aqueous electrolyte studies. We did not perform further analyses beyond standard Raman and conductivity characteristics as the details of boron doping of diamond are not the subject of the present study, and it has been extensively analyzed in the literature.^{24,27,28}

The structural and structural-chemical features of the surfaces of the B-MCD and C-GCEs were investigated. Figure 1a,b shows a general view of the two working electrodes used for electrochemical studies. SEM images of the B-MCD surfaces were obtained at different magnifications before (Figure 1c,d) and after (Figure 1f,g) the electrochemical studies.

A difference in the surface structure is evident, explained by the chemical etching of the B-MCD surface during electro-

chemical studies in solutions of 1–12 m aqueous electrolyte NaNO₃. Such an etching process has been recently studied in a prior study.²² The etching mechanism was attributed to the preferential etching of sp^2 carbon phases localized at the dislocations and grain boundaries by highly concentrated nitrate salts at elevated temperatures. A similar effect most likely occurs here by electrochemical cycling in WiS at room temperature.

Boron doping itself can generally affect the morphology and diamond properties.²⁹ It helps eliminate nondiamond phases such as graphite, improving the overall purity and quality of the diamond film. It also increases the diamond nucleation density, which results in generally smaller grain sizes. However, these effects are well below the morphological effect due to WiS etching.

For comparison, SEM images of the surfaces of the two working electrodes, B-MCD and C-GC, were obtained at different magnifications after electrochemical studies (Figure 1h,i). A different surface structure is observed for both electrodes. B-MCD electrode has a porous structure, while the C-GC electrode has a polished surface with minor irregularities (pores, cracks). For the chemical composition analysis of the surface, Raman spectra (excitation 442 nm) were obtained for the two electrodes (Figure 1e). For B-MCDE, B_1 (453 cm^{-1}) and B_2 (1200 cm^{-1}), peaks associated with the boron incorporated into the film, ZCP_D (1280 cm^{-1}), belong to the remains of the zone center phonon mode of diamond and is shifted to lower wavenumber due to the “Fano effect,” G (1540 cm^{-1}), the graphitic content. For C-GCE: D – 1370 cm^{-1} ; G – 1594 cm^{-1} ; 2D – 2730 cm^{-1} ; D+G – 2950 cm^{-1} .

In contrast to the B-MCD electrode, the Raman spectrum of the C-GCE shows features typical of glassy carbon.

3.2. CV on B-MCDE; pH and Conductivity of NaNO₃ WiS Electrolyte. The CV was measured with two working electrodes, B-MCDE and C-GCE, in WiS electrolyte NaNO₃ in concentrations from 1 to 12 m. Typical CV characteristics

Figure 3. EIS of NaNO₃ aqueous electrolyte (1–12 m concentrations) using (a) B-MCDE and (b) C-GCE. Equivalent electrical circuit correlated with the electrode interface structural scheme for (c) B-MCDE and (d) C-GCE.

are shown in Figure 2a,b, where the cathode and anode scans are shown after the initial three cycles to reach a steady state of the system. After the initial cycling, the CV characteristics are stable. The B-MCD electrode etching in WiS (see Figure 1) is thus self-saturated.

The C-GCE exhibits capacitive currents that are higher than those of the B-MCD electrode in the WiS electrolyte. This is a well-documented feature observed, for instance, when glassy carbon was compared with Au and Pt electrodes in a WiS electrolyte.³⁰ It corroborates superior performance of B-MCD electrodes compared to conventional C-GCE and metal electrodes.

The CV scans were used to estimate the ESW. The comparison of the changes in ESW with the changes in the concentration of NaNO₃ aqueous electrolyte for two types of electrodes, B-MCD and C-GC, are shown in Figure S2 and summarized in Table S1. The ESW was estimated for different electrode areas. Figure S3 shows the optical microscopic images of B-MCDE and C-GCE. The estimated area of the B-MCDE, according to the microscopic image, was 0.023 cm². C-GCE area calculated accordingly to the diameter $d = 3$ mm was 0.071 cm².

In general, the ESW expansion to ~ 3 V is observed for B-MCDE in the whole electrolyte concentration range (1–12 m), which is slightly higher compared to C-GCE (~ 2.7 V). Based on the SEM surface morphologies and Raman spectra (see Figures 1 and S1), we assume that this is primarily due to the differences in the microstructure variation (flat vs nano)

and surface chemical composition (crystalline diamond vs amorphous sp² carbon) of the two types of electrodes. The concentration of boron-doped also influences the surface as a change in grain orientation.³¹ Accordingly, different atomic surface terminations and surface energy band structures can also affect electrode surface conductivity and electrochemical interactions.^{32,33} In the whole studied concentration range of NaNO₃ electrolyte, the ESW of B-MCDE remains around 3 V, with only small variations that may be due to experimental uncertainty. Thus, it can be assumed that ESW practically does not change in the studied range of concentrations and it is always above ESW of C-GCE. This fact will allow use of WiS NaNO₃ electrolytes of much lower concentrations as an electrolyte for SCs with the B-MCD anode.

Figure 2c shows the dependence of pH on the molality concentration of NaNO₃ in aqueous electrolytes. The electrolyte pH is 5.9–6.8 for all concentrations (1–12 m). At 1 m concentration, pH can be considered very close to the most acidic 2m, whereas conductivity drops down there due to much less salt in the electrolyte. The pH then increases with the concentration to a neutral condition at 8 m and remains practically unchanged. Figure 2d shows that the conductivity of NaNO₃ aqueous electrolyte also increases with the concentration, reaching a maximum of 187 mS/cm at 8 m and then decreasing slightly toward 12 m. It depends on decreasing free water molecules with increasing NaNO₃ salt concentration in the WiS electrolyte.³ The observed behavior represents a sophisticated electrochemical interaction characteristic of

Table 1. Fitting Parameters of Equivalent Electrical Circuits at Different Concentrations of NaNO₃ Aqueous Electrolytes on the B-MCDE and C-GCE

B-MCDE							
concentration (molality)	R_s (Ω)	R_{ct} (Ω)	C_{dl} (μF)	CPE – Y_0 (Mho*s ^{^N})	CPE – N	χ^2	
1	93.1	88.8	3.21	1.08×10^{-6}	0.932	0.021	
2	64.9	36.3	2.69	1.05×10^{-6}	0.935	0.018	
4	53.7	32.3	2.30	1.01×10^{-6}	0.934	0.026	
6	57	56.2	2.88	1.04×10^{-6}	0.937	0.029	
8	49.1	50.7	1.92	1.03×10^{-6}	0.935	0.046	
10	49.8	50.9	1.73	1.03×10^{-6}	0.936	0.052	
12	47.4	55	1.50	1.05×10^{-6}	0.938	0.055	
C-GCE							
concentration (molality)	R_s (Ω)	R_{ct} (Ω)	CPE 1 – Y_0 (Mho*s ^{^N})	CPE 1 – N	CPE 2 – Y_0 (Mho*s ^{^N})	CPE 2 – N	χ^2
1	37.6	82,338	7.03×10^{-6}	0.799	8.03×10^{-6}	0.565	0.015
2	23.6	1382	7.51×10^{-6}	0.805	6.02×10^{-6}	0.348	0.03
4	16.1	161,060	8.85×10^{-6}	0.778	7.61×10^{-6}	0.558	0.029
6	15	153	5.05×10^{-6}	0.835	7.51×10^{-6}	0.385	0.027
8	14.9	261	5.97×10^{-6}	0.822	6.87×10^{-6}	0.374	0.048
10	14.8	124,650	7.50×10^{-6}	0.792	8.30×10^{-6}	0.684	0.032
12	12.5	74,504	8.05×10^{-6}	0.801	8.31×10^{-6}	0.584	0.045

concentrated salt systems, reflecting complex ionic and molecular dynamics commonly observed in WiS systems.

The above results show that B-MCD electrodes could be promising for anodes in SCs based on the NaNO₃ WiS electrolyte, even at low salt concentrations down to 1 m. In all cases, the hydrogen and oxygen evolution potentials are shifted far beyond the thermodynamic stability limit of water.³ Thus, oxygen and hydrogen evolution seems to be inhibited at all concentrations. It is well-known that WiS electrolytes can widen ESW in general.³⁴ However, it cannot be only the effect of the NaNO₃ WiS electrolyte. ESW is higher than previously observed on NaNO₃ WiS electrolyte with stainless steel electrodes (ESW was 2.22 for 1 m and 2.56 V for 12 m)³ or than observed with C-GCE (ESW ~ 2.7 V for 1–12 m). Thus, the large ESW ~ 3 V must be due to specific features of the B-MCD electrode. This assertion is supported by the fact that NaNO₃ aqueous electrolytes can widen ESW via thermodynamic and kinetic factors.³⁴ Kinetic factors can be more direct than thermodynamic factors because the reactions happen at the electrode interface. The electrode–electrolyte interface layer ensures electrochemical stability at anodic potentials. An electric double layer of salt ions keeps water away from the electrode at the cathodic potentials, thereby suppressing oxygen evolution.

Direct comparison of flat and nanoporous B-MCDE morphology in WiS is not possible as the nanoporous surface is the inherent feature arising on B-MCDE in WiS. Nevertheless in a prior study,²² B-UNCD electrode performances as a capacitor in sodium perchlorate were compared before and after the thermal salt treatment, i.e., with original and nanoporous-like surface morphology, showing obvious benefit of the latter. Thus, we can safely assume that a similar effect will be at play on B-MCDE after electrochemical etching in WiS.

3.3. EIS. To evaluate the transport kinetics during the electrochemical reaction, EIS measurements of aqueous NaNO₃ solutions (concentrations 1–12 m) were performed with two-electrode configurations in a frequency range from 0.1 Hz to 100 kHz, where B-MCDE and C-GCE were used as working electrodes. The Nyquist plots with the magnified high-

frequency region are shown as the insets in Figure 3a,b. The Nyquist plots do not exhibit pronounced semicircles due to the nature of the low R_{ct} and R_s in the WiS electrolyte.

We tested different equivalent electrical circuits using Nova version 2.1.6 software (Table S2). It was impossible to obtain the same electrical circuit for the two electrodes; one circuit fitted one electrode well but did not fit the other. We tested multiple equivalent electrical circuits (see Table S2). Different equivalent circuits were then selected that provided the best fitting of the Nyquist and Bode plots: R-CPE(CR) for the B-MCDE and R(CPE[R-CPE]) for the C-GCE (Figure 3c,d). Different equivalent electrical circuits are due to the different surface and material qualities of the two electrodes. Both electrodes have different degrees of roughness and various geometric defects, confirmed by the obtained SEM images of the electrode surfaces (Figure 1h,i), as schematically shown in Figure 3c,d.

For the entire range of concentrations of 1–12 m NaNO₃ aqueous electrolytes, the fitting parameters for the two electrodes were obtained, which are given in Table 1.

Both electrodes are characterized by a low series resistance R_s , which decreases with increasing concentration of NaNO₃ salt in the electrolyte. The electrolyte resistance R_s for 1 m NaNO₃ with B-MCDE was 93.1 Ω , while for the C-GCE, it was 37.6 Ω . The resistance values for 12 m NaNO₃ electrolyte were 47.4 Ω for B-MCDE and 12.5 Ω for C-GCE. For both electrodes, the series resistance R_s decreased by more than half with an increasing NaNO₃ salt concentration from 1 to 12 m.

In contrast to the series resistance R_s , the resistance value associated with charge transport R_{ct} varied nonmonotonically for both electrodes, which is associated with a different degree of surface roughness at the electrode–electrolyte interface. The nonmonotonic R_{ct} changes with increasing salt concentration for B-MCDE, in contrast to that of the C-GCE, are due to the high porosity of the surface of the B-MCDE and the inhomogeneous adsorption of salt ions on its surface. Charge-transfer resistance for B-MCDE varied within 1 order of magnitude up to 36%. In contrast, for C-GCE, the value of R_{ct} was changing abruptly by 3 orders of magnitude with an increase in the salt concentration. The jumpy nature of the

Figure 4. Raman spectra (excitation 532 nm) of different concentrations of WiS NaNO_3 electrolytes: (a) N–O stretching vibration of NO_3^- ; (b) O–H stretching vibration in H_2O molecules. Deconvolution of a Raman spectrum of O–H stretching vibration: (c) 1–6 m $\text{NaNO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (d) 8–12 m $\text{NaNO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

dependence of R_{ct} on the electrolyte concentration can be due to the surface structure of the C-GCE, its insulation, and chemical composition, which was confirmed by SEM and Raman spectra (Figure 1e). These features corroborate better the conductive properties of the B-MCDE compared with the commercial C-GCE. The low charge-transfer resistance R_{ct} for the B-MCDE in the presence of NaNO_3 aqueous electrolyte is related to the high electrical conductivity of boron-doped microcrystalline diamond and its surface's chemical and structural features. The lowest resistance R_{ct} was observed for concentrations of 2–4 m. The value of the double-layer capacitance of the C_{dl} for the B-MCDE monotonically decreased with increasing electrolyte concentration from 1 to 12 m and was equal to 3.21–1.50 μF , respectively. This is due to an increase in the thickness of the double-electric layer at the electrode-electrolyte interface, which is due to the decrease of free water molecules with an increase of salt concentration in the electrolyte and the high degree of surface roughness of the B-MCDE.

Analyzing the Bode plots (Figure S4a,b) for B-MCD and C-GC electrodes, a significant difference in impedance values at low frequencies is observed ($Z \sim 1 \text{ M}\Omega$ for B-MCDE and $\sim 100 \text{ k}\Omega$ for C-GCE), and at $f = 10 \text{ kHz}$, the impedance value Z was $\sim 100 \Omega$ for B-MCDE and $\sim 50 \Omega$ for C-GCE. The impedance decreases slightly, and at 100 kHz, it was $\sim 90 \Omega$ for B-MCDE and $\sim 40 \Omega$ for C-GCE. CPE was used instead of the Warburg element (Figure 3d) for a better fitting result of the

C-GCE. The obtained values of N were in the range 0.35–0.68, which may be due to the influence of surface effects associated with structural irregularities of the C-GCE surface. In contrast, in the B-MCDE, diffusion effects at low frequencies are absent based on fitting by the equivalent electrical model (Figure 3c).

The comparison of the two electrodes shows better conductive and capacitive properties of the B-MCDE in comparison to the C-GCE.

The IDE electrodes were used to analyze the impedance behavior of the NaNO_3 aqueous electrolyte in interaction with other metal electrodes (Au and Pt) (Figure S5a,b) respectively. The experimental Nyquist plots of NaNO_3 electrolyte 1–12 m concentrations with gold (Au) and platinum (Pt) IDE sensors were obtained at frequency up to 100 kHz. Analysis of the Nyquist plots for all concentrations of sodium nitrate electrolyte with different electrodes, B-MCDE, Au, and Pt, in two-electrode configurations demonstrated similar changes. The same nature of changes in the Nyquist plots for B-MCDE and metallic (Au/Pt) electrodes indicates that the B-MCD material has a metal-like conductivity.

The 12 m NaNO_3 aqueous electrolyte at a room temperature of $+23 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was unstable (small salt crystals were observed). An optical image of salt crystals in 12 m WiS NaNO_3 electrolyte is shown in Figure S6a. At 12 m salt concentrations, adsorption of the formed salt crystals was observed on the surface of the B-MCDE (Figure S6b). This is

due to the influence of the structural features of the B-MCDE surface, namely, significant surface roughness, porosity, and the presence of micropores and microchannels for rapid diffusion of ions, which is also confirmed by refs 6 and 35.

3.4. Chemical and Structural Characterizations of NaNO_3 WiS Electrolyte. Generally, the structural features of the NaNO_3 WiS electrolytes were investigated by Raman spectroscopy and discussed in some of the recent articles.^{3,36,37} Here, we performed Raman spectra of WiS NaNO_3 electrolytes at different concentrations, which are present in Figure 4a,b.

The N–O stretching vibration of NO_3 anions (Figure 4a) shifted from 1058 cm^{-1} (ν_1) for concentrations 1–6 m NaNO_3 water-electrolyte to 1062 cm^{-1} for concentrations 8–12 m NaNO_3 WiS electrolytes. The O–H stretching region of the Raman spectrum of aqueous solutions of NaNO_3 is the set of broad bands between 2900 and 3700 cm^{-1} . A pure H_2O reference solution has peak positions at 3.223 cm^{-1} (P_1), 3.433 cm^{-1} (P_2), and 3.617 cm^{-1} (P_3) (Figure S7). The morphology of the Raman bands is influenced by the presence of NaNO_3 in the aqueous solution. The O–H stretching region for pure water and the salt NaNO_3 dissolved in it correlates with the spectra obtained for aqueous solutions of 38, i.e., a characteristic shift and narrowing of the spectrum is observed with increasing salt concentration. The O–H stretching vibrations of water molecules (Figure 4b) in 1–6 m concentrations of NaNO_3 water electrolytes have the same nature as in pure water with two peaks at 3230 cm^{-1} (ν_2) and 3420 cm^{-1} (ν_3). With an increasing concentration of the NaNO_3 salt from 8 to 12 m, the O–H stretching was sensitive to the molecular environment. A new peak appears at 3512 cm^{-1} (ν_4), which can be attributed to hydration with sodium ions and decrease of “free water” for a concentration of NaNO_3 higher than 6 m. A similar change in the Raman spectra is also observed in WiS NaCl electrolyte, where there is a linear increase in the relative wavenumber with increasing salinity of the electrolyte.³⁸ This peak (P_1) (Figure 4d) is characteristic of the WiS electrolytes, and it can be directly correlated with the conductivity of WiS electrolytes.

The morphology of the spectral region is characterized by deconvolution using three Gaussian–Lorentzian contributions. Deconvolution spectra shown in Figure 4c,d were made to compare measurements made on pure water drops ($3\text{ }\mu\text{L}$) and WiS NaNO_3 electrolyte (1–12 m).

The analysis of the curves obtained by Raman spectroscopy is correlated with the measured impedance data for the studied liquids in the given concentration range of 1–12 m NaNO_3 . Changes are observed in both the constructed Nyquist curves and in the Raman spectra, particularly for 8–12 m WiS NaNO_3 electrolyte, due to increased salt concentration and decreased free water molecules in the highly concentrated studied samples.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The features of electrochemical interaction of WiS sodium nitrate electrolyte in a wide range of concentrations (1–12 m) with a working electrode B-MCD compared to a C-GCE were analyzed. Almost over the entire studied range of NaNO_3 aqueous electrolyte concentrations (1–12 m), the ESW was $\sim 3\text{ V}$, higher than the previously reported 2.56 V for (12 m WiS NaNO_3) on stainless steel electrodes and in comparison with C-GCE ($\sim 2.7\text{ V}$). This fact will allow to use WiS NaNO_3 electrolytes of much lower concentrations as an electrolyte for SCs with the B-MCD anode. For all NaNO_3 electrolyte

concentrations of 1–12 m according to the estimated EIS parameters according to the selected equivalent electrical circuits, the B-MCDE demonstrated better conductive and capacitive properties than the C-GCE. Low charge series resistance R_s and charge-transfer resistance R_{ct} ($<100\text{ }\Omega$) and also a good capacitive property ($3.21\text{--}1.50\text{ }\mu\text{F}$) for all $\text{NaNO}_3/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ electrolyte concentrations are explained by the structural and chemical features of the surface of the B-MCDE, in particular, the high degree of roughness and the presence of a large number of micropores and channels for facilitating diffusion of ions. Raman spectroscopy confirms the presence of boron in the B-MCDE and shows significant changes in the structure of the WiS NaNO_3 electrolyte at concentrations higher than 6 m, which correlates with the EIS data. Due to its extended ESW of $\sim 3\text{ V}$, good conductive properties, and structural and chemical features, B-MCD is a promising material as an anode for practical use in water-salt SCs in combination with WiS NaNO_3 electrolytes even at lower concentrations.

Microcrystalline thin film boron-doped diamond is, nowadays, not an expensive material. It has been considered for large-area dye-sensitized solar cell applications or large-scale water purification systems. The results presented here may thus motivate such large-scale application studies also in the area of supercapacitors.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Data Availability Statement

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article and Supporting Information and also are available from the corresponding author upon request. Raw data are also available from Zenodo online repository: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14266747.

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jpcc.5c00414>.

Chamber of the microwave plasma CVD system; AFM of encapsulated B-MCD film; Raman spectra of B-MCD compared to intrinsic microcrystalline diamond; SEM surface morphology; comparison of B-MCDE and C-GCE ESW of WiS NaNO_3 electrolyte for different concentrations 1–12 m; ESW of WiS NaNO_3 electrolytes on B-MCD and C-GC electrodes; optical images of B-MCDE and C-GCE surface; fitting for 6 m concentrations of NaNO_3 water electrolytes on B-MCDE and C-GCE; Bode plots; Nyquist plots; NaNO_3 salt crystals; and deconvolution of a Raman spectrum of O–H stretching vibration in H_2O (PDF)

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ESW, electrochemical stability window; SCs, supercapacitors; NaNO_3 , sodium nitrate; WiS, water-in-salt; B-MCDE, boron-doped microcrystalline diamond; C-GCE, commercial glassy carbon electrode; CVD, chemical vapor deposition; TMB, trimethyl boron; sccm, standard cubic centimeters per minute; CV, cyclic voltammetry; EIS, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

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